

Preparation and Characterization of Adsorbents for Carbon dioxide Adsorption

Stephen O. Akpasi, and Yusuf M. Isa

Abstract— To reduce emissions of greenhouse gasses, there should be better control of the release of CO₂ due to human activities. In this study, an inexpensive material was developed as adsorbents for CO₂ capture. For the preparation of activated carbon by chemical activation in a laboratory vacuum furnace with zinc chloride (ZnCl₂) at 500 °C for 1 hour, sugarcane bagasse was being used as a starting material whereas kaolinite was locally obtained. These adsorbents were applied for the storage of CO₂ within a range of temperatures (30 °C, 50 °C and 70°C) while the flow rate (30mL/min to 70mL/min) and column bed height (3cm – 5cm) were varied at constant temperature. This research also explored sample features such as the surface area and porosity, functional groups, and scanning electron microscopic images. This further substantiate the conclusion that CO₂ adsorption with kaolinite and activated carbon is favoured at low temperatures, low operating CO₂ flowrates and high column bed height.

Index Terms—sugarcane bagasse, activated carbon, carbonization, chemical activation, adsorption.

1. INTRODUCTION

Activated carbon is a porous substance with a broad specific surface area ideal for the adsorption of gases and aqueous solution solutes. This is due to activated carbon properties that have a large active surface area that can provide high capacity for adsorption, excellent porous structures and efficient mechanical characteristics [1, 2]. Therefore, it has been widely used to separate gases, recover solvents, eliminate organic contaminants from drinking water and support catalysts. The need for activated carbon is rising as environmental pollution is becoming a more significant problem. It is a flexible adsorbent due to its excellent adsorption properties. Moreover, activated carbon is most commonly used because it is possible to design and modify most chemicals (e.g, surface groups) and physical properties (e.g. surface area and pore size distribution) according to the required specifications[3]. In addition, because of its simplicity of operation, the adsorption on activated carbon tends to be the most common techniques, since the sorbent material can be

processed extremely efficiently, easily handled and regenerated in some cases [4].

Activated carbons are made of a range of materials from carbonaceous sources. The selection of the precursor depends primarily on the availability, cost, and the quality of the product. However, the production process and the specific intent of the product are also critical factors [5]. Several other agricultural byproducts were often used in recent years as sources of activated carbon owing to their affordability at low costs, widely available, and sustainable resources. Agricultural biomass waste has become a promising raw material for activated carbon production [5]. They have been used to manufacture activated carbon because of their high carbon content, high adsorption capacity, high density, and considerably mechanical strength. They also have a low ash content that is adequate within the activated carbon system to create highly porous structures. Many agricultural waste materials have been identified to be effective precursors of activated carbon owing to their low ash and high carbon content, including sugar cane bagasse waste, coconut shell[5, 6], grain sorghum[5], coffee bean husks[5], rubber wood sawdust[5], chestnut wood[5], and fruit stones[5]. In addition, mineral clay is also one of the most available natural materials and is therefore available at a minimal cost. It is possible to substantially extend the use of clays for adsorption and separation. To our best understanding, very few studies have explored kaolinite for CO₂ capture so far and studied extensively the parameters relating to its capacity for adsorption. Most research efforts have concentrated on clay minerals from an industrial perspective. In this research, therefore, sugarcane bagasse was chosen as a starting material to produce activated carbon. In addition, kaolinite was also selected as an adsorbent for CO₂ capture via adsorption since both materials are readily available in South Africa (sugarcane bagasse and kaolinite) but have very limited market value.

Due to its efficient natural structure and low ash content, Sugarcane Bagasse (SCB) is ideal for producing activated carbon. SCB is a by-product of the sugarcane industry harvested after juice extraction for the manufacture of sugar. These agricultural products can contribute positively to the processing of sugar cane bagasse into activated carbons that can be used as adsorbents, an ion exchange, carbon molecular sieve, catalyst, dramatically alleviate waste disposal costs and provide a fairly inexpensive alternative to conventional commercial carbon products. Carbonization of the precursors at high temperatures in an inert environment supported by the activation phase is the most common technique used for activated carbon preparation. The method of activation is categorized into physical and chemical processes. The physical

Manuscript submitted October 19, 2020.

S. O. Akpasi is with the Durban University of Technology, Department of Chemical Engineering, S4 Level 1, Steve Biko Campus, Steve Biko Road, Durban, 4001. SOUTH AFRICA (e-mail: stephenakpasi48@gmail.com).

Y. M. Isa is with the Department of Chemical Engineering, Durban University of Technology, Steve Biko Campus, Durban, 4001. SOUTH AFRICA (e-mail: YusufI@dut.ac.za).

activation method includes treatment of char resulting from carbonization with oxidizing gases at a high temperature, usually steam or carbon dioxide (400 to 1000 °C) [7]. The starting material is mixed with an activating reagent during the chemical activation process and the mixture is heated in an inert atmosphere [8, 9]. In contrast to physical activation, this process is typically performed at lower temperature and activation time, higher surface area efficiency and better porosity.

The objective of this study is to prepare sugar cane bagasse from activated carbon by chemical activation employing zinc chloride ($ZnCl_2$) to absorb CO_2 from its source, such as flue gas. To further study the performance of CO_2 adsorption on activated carbon and kaolinite materials. In this paper, these adsorbents were applied for the storage of CO_2 within a range of temperatures (30°C, 50°C and 70°C) while the flow rate (30mL/min to 70mL/min) and column bed height (3cm to 5cm) were varied at constant temperature. This research also explored sample features such as surface area and porosity, functional groups, and scanning electron microscopic images.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Raw material

Sugarcane Bagasse Waste (SBW) was chosen for the preparation of activated carbon. SBW was purchased from Umfolozi sugar mill (PTY) LTD, KwaZulu-Natal in South Africa. To extract dust and impurities, the materials were washed several times with distilled water, while the kaolinite was acquired from G & W mineral resources in Germiston, South Africa. To eliminate any surface moisture, SBW samples were later dried in the laboratory oven at 110 °C for 24h and then grounded and sieved to a particle size range of 150-250 μm . The precursor's proximate analysis yielded 6.4% humidity, 31% volatile matter, 60% fixed carbon and 2.6% ash.

Fig. 1. (a) Sugarcane bagasse waste (b) Grinded sugarcane bagasse (c) Kaolinite

2.2 Activation Preparation

2.2.1 Chemical activation

With $ZnCl_2$ chemical activation of the powdered precursor was performed. 10g of dried precursor was mixed well with 100 ml of solution containing 10g of $ZnCl_2$. In this case, the chemical ratio was 100% (activating agent / precursor). The mixing was carried out at a temperature of 50 °C for 1h. After mixing, the slurry was vacuum-dried for 24 h at 100 °C. As shown in Fig. 3(a), the resulting chemically loaded samples were then placed into a horizontal kiln furnace. To create an inert atmosphere inside the reactor and transport the volatile compounds, nitrogen gas flow of 200 mL / min was applied. The reactor was heated to 500 °C and held for about 1 h (a heating rate of 10 °C / min) at this temperature. After completion of the activation process, the reactor was cooled to room temperature, and the char was collected and washed with distilled water approximately 5 times to effectively remove any residual Zn, preceded by drying at 80 °C until the solution is neutralized to obtain activated carbon (SBAC). Finally, the product of SBAC were ground to a fine powder (< 250 μm) as shown in Fig. 3(b) and stored for the adsorption experiment.

Fig. 2. Procedure for preparing activated carbon

Fig. 3. (a) Horizontal kiln furnace (b) Activated carbon

2.3 CO_2 adsorption experiment

An adsorption column was used to perform the CO_2 adsorption test. For these experiments 99 % CO_2 was used. In each experiment, the column was filled with 3.0 g of adsorbents

(packing height $\approx 5.0\text{cm}$) and placed within a temperature control bath to maintain a constant temperature at 30°C . The operating flow rate was varied from (30-70) mL/min at constant temperature. The temperature of the thermostatic water bath was kept constant throughout the experiment. At each temperature (30, 50 and 70°C), the experiment was allowed to run for 1200 seconds (20 minutes). The height of the bed was varied from 3-5cm at each run to study the behaviour of the adsorbents. This experiment was monitored and recorded; the change in the mass of the sample was determined by equation 3.3 below and the amount of CO_2 adsorbed was calculated.

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ adsorption capacity} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 1000 \quad (3.1)$$

Where W_2 = weight of adsorbent after adsorption
 W_1 = weight of adsorbent before adsorption

Fig. 4. Process flow diagram of the adsorption set-up

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 SEM analysis

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique was used to examine the surface physical morphology of the sugarcane bagasse derived activated carbon (SBAC) and kaolinite material. Figure 4 displays SEM images of sugarcane bagasse (at optimum operating conditions before and after carbonization) and kaolinite material with a magnification of 50,000X at a resolution of $2\mu\text{m}$, $5\mu\text{m}$ and $20\mu\text{m}$. This became possible to observe pores of various sizes and shapes. The micrograph images in Fig. (5b) can be seen that the exterior surface is full of caking and aggregation of chemically activated carbon, existing on the char structure and therefore leading to the formation of chars with an intact external surface. According to the micrograph, the higher aggregates seemed to have been derived from the evaporation of ZnCl_2 during carbonization, rendering the space previously occupied by the ZnCl_2 .

Interestingly, with the activation of the sugarcane bagasse with ZnCl_2 , the carbon structure of the sample increases and begins to cohere and form sphere-shaped porous variable-size structures. These structures can assist in the movement of CO_2

gas molecules through a broad range of adsorption sites. This demonstrates that activation removes hydrocarbons, which enhances the adsorption capacity of activated carbon. Discrete aggregation was shown in Fig. (5c) and was characterized by the presence of few mesopores and made spherical, making the surface rough.

Fig. 5. Scanning electron microscopy images of sugarcane bagasse (a) before carbonization (b) after carbonization at 500°C (c) kaolinite

3.2 BET surface area

Table 1 shows the BET surface area for sugar cane based activated carbon and kaolinite. The obtained BET surface area was substantially high, which is within the appropriate range of commercial activated carbon ($500\text{-}1500\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). Generally, with a high BET surface area, results in higher adsorption capacity because activated carbon is capable to adsorb a number of gases under different conditions [10].

We observed that for the chemical activated sample of sugarcane bagasse, A higher surface area was generated by SBAC, $979\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ compared to kaolinite, $584\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. This is because ZnCl_2 has helped to generate more new pores and expand the existing pores as the activating agent. The maximum pore volume ($0.43\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$) was also displayed by the chemical activated SBW, followed by kaolinite ($0.26\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$), indicating greater gas adsorption. At this moment, adsorption of CO_2 was not only related to BET surface area and pore volume, but also depended on reaction occurred between adsorbate (CO_2) and adsorbent (loaded AC) and kaolinite samples.

Table I. BET surface area

Sample	BET surface area (m^2/g)	Total pore volume (cm^3/g)	Average pore diameter (\AA)
Chemical activated carbon from SBW	712	0.43	18.77
Kaolinite	484	0.26	14.09

3.3 FTIR analysis

The FT-IR test results of sugar cane based activated carbon before and after CO_2 adsorption are presented in Fig. 6 whereas the FT-IR test results of kaolinite before and after the adsorption of CO_2 are depicted in Fig. 7. The functional group analysis was conducted at a range of $500\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ wavelengths.

Fig. 6. The FTIR spectrum of sugar cane based activated carbon before and after adsorption

Table II: FTIR spectral characteristics of activated carbon derived from sugar cane before and after adsorption

Activated carbon before adsorption	Activated carbon after adsorption	Assignment
3674	3671	OH-stretch (in alcohol)
542	537	C-H bending
1103	1091	C-O stretch (in aliphatic ether)
1741	1844	C=O stretch (in anhydride)

The variations in the FTIR spectrum of activated carbon derived from sugar cane bagasse can be shown in figure 4.2 before and after CO₂ adsorption. A description of the features of the shifted bands and the existing functional groups is presented in Table II. As seen in Fig. 6, the activated carbon derived from the sugar cane bagasse spectrum displaced an absorption peak of 3671 cm⁻¹ clearly indicating the presence of an O-H functional group. First, the broad peak at 3671 cm⁻¹ shifted and became weak at 3641 cm⁻¹ due to the O-H stretch and the H-bonding of the hydroxyl group in alcohols and phenols. The asymmetry of this band indicates the presence of strong hydrogen bonds.

Table II: FTIR spectral characteristics of kaolinite before and after adsorption

Kaolinite before adsorption	Kaolinite after adsorption	Assignment
3305	3482	OH-stretch (in alcohol)

The peak 537 cm⁻¹ which shifted to 542 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of the C-H group. A strong band at 1844 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1741 cm⁻¹, attributed to the C=O groups of anhydride compounds. Whereas for the kaolinite spectrum before and after adsorption of CO₂ in Fig. 7, there is an absorption peak of 3305cm⁻¹ shifted to 3482 cm⁻¹ confirming the formation of O-H group that may incorporate water, alcohol, and phenol components. The comparison of the sugar cane derived activated carbon FTIR spectra before and after CO₂ adsorption indicates the change in the spectrum that occurred and it can be said that the adsorbent's functional groups were actively engaged in the adsorption process [11]. Overall, it can be concluded that the sugar cane bagasse derived activated carbon has functional groups that can help bind or trap particles including alcohols, phenols, alkanes, and alkyl halides. The hydroxyl group has a strong affinity to pollutants and heavy metal ions [12].

3.4 CO₂ adsorption

3.4.1 Effect of temperature

Fig. 8 (a) illustrates behaviour showing the effect of temperature on the CO₂ adsorption capacity for SBAC and kaolinite. From 30 – 70 °C, the effect of temperature was examined. It is expected that the temperature will influence the nature of the adsorption that occurred, i.e., physisorption or chemisorption. In other words, an increase in the temperature of adsorption results in a decrease in the amount of CO₂ adsorbed. Increased temperature gives more internal energy to CO₂ molecules during the gas phase. We observed that the increased energy allows the diffusion of gaseous molecules at a higher

rate. However, at the same time, the chances of CO₂ being restricted or trapped on the adsorbent surface by adsorption sites of fixed energy is decreased. The highest adsorption capacity was obtained at 30 °C for SBAC and kaolinite systems at 28.97 mgCO₂/kg AC and 12.98 mgCO₂/kg kaolinite, respectively. The observed trend is that CO₂ adsorption decreased with an increase in temperature. The kinetic energy of gases increases with temperature at a constant flow rate, leading to less surface coverage of CO₂ gases. The observed trend can be attributed to the exothermic nature of the adsorption process. The principle of Le Chatelier illustrates this when it is used to predict the degree of an exothermic process, stating that increasing the temperature would decrease the exothermic reaction magnitude.

Fig. 8. Effect of Temperature on the adsorbent systems at fixed 30mL/min flowrate of 5cm column height

3.4.2 Effect of flowrate

Fig. 9 depicts the effect of flowrate on CO₂ adsorption capacity of SBAC and kaolinite systems. The highest CO₂ adsorbed was achieved using a flowrate of 30 mL/min. The CO₂ adsorbed with a flowrate of 40mL/min, 50mL/min, 60mL/min, and 70mL/min were lower than that achieved with a flowrate of 30 mL/min. We observed that decreasing the inlet flow rate of the gas increases the contact time and improves mass transfer between CO₂ and the adsorbents. That is, lower flow rates increase the retention time of the CO₂ molecules on the selected adsorbents within the packed bed adsorption column resulting in the high amount of CO₂ adsorbed. At a lower flow rate, adsorbate (CO₂) has more time to contact with the adsorbent that resulted in a higher adsorption capacity of CO₂ [13]. Longer residence times are required for a higher amount of CO₂ to be adsorbed and entrapped in the pores of the adsorbents. As a result of the aforementioned reasons, the maximum amount of CO₂ adsorbed at a constant temperature of 30 °C by sugarcane based activated carbon and kaolinite systems at different flow rates of 30mL/min, 40mL/min, 50mL/min, 60mL/min and 70 mL/min CO₂ were 20.45, 19.62, 16.82, 14.70 and 12.11 mgCO₂/kg adsorbent as depicted in the

Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Effect of Flowrate on the adsorbent systems at a fixed 5cm column height of different temperatures

3.4.3 Effect of column height

When the bed height increased, the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent systems also increased; the determined heights of bed were 3, 4 and 5cm to examine the effect on the CO₂ adsorption performance of sugarcane based activated carbon and kaolinite systems. The flow rate was kept constant at about 30 mL/min to 70mL/min. The effect of the bed height for CO₂ adsorption onto SBAC and kaolinite samples at heights of 3, 4, and 5 cm is shown in Fig. 10, which indicated that CO₂ adsorption capacity for the bed heights of 3–5 cm were increasing. The highest adsorption capacity of CO₂ for SBAC and kaolinite systems was achieved at the height of 5cm. More interaction opportunities between CO₂ gas and adsorbent particles may also be due to the good performance of CO₂ adsorption on sugar cane-based activated carbon at a bed height of 5.0 cm. However, since an increase in bed height induces greater resistance to mass transfer and slower kinetics of adsorption, the mass transfer zone had also broadened[14]. This was due to an increase in surface area and the number of available adsorption binding sites. The time for interaction of adsorbate and adsorbent also increased with an increasing amount of adsorbent [15, 16]

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the help received from Mrs. J. N. Thiloshini and Mr. R. K. Dwari of DUT Research Laboratory, Durban, South Africa for porosity analysis of samples.

Fig. 10. Effect of column height on the adsorbent systems at fixed 30mL/min flowrate of different temperatures

CONCLUSIONS

This analysis found that the chemical activation of sugarcane bagasse waste with ZnCl₂ as activating agent can prepare a relatively good surface area activated carbons. The release of moisture and ZnCl₂ constitutes much of the evolution throughout the carbonization of the ZnCl₂ treated sample, suggesting that ZnCl₂ plays a significant role in increasing the surface area during carbonization. However, kaolinite, a cheap and commonly available clay mineral can also be utilized for CO₂ capture as it acts as a pollutant collector. The study of various parameters during CO₂ capture via adsorption revealed that temperature, flowrate, and column height influences the amount of CO₂ adsorbed. Under examined experimental conditions, for the production of a high surface area activated carbon from sugarcane bagasse waste by chemical activation, the optimum conditions are chemical ratio (activating agent/precursor) of 100%, carbonization time of 1 h and carbonization temperature of 500 °C. At this optimal condition, the BET surface area obtained were 712 m²/g and 484 m²/g for sugarcane based activated carbon (SBAC) and kaolinite samples, respectively. The properties of SBAC and kaolinite samples were characterized in terms of FT-IR, the BET surface area and SEM. The FT-IR results revealed all the functional groups of the adsorbent that were actively involved in the adsorption process. According to BET, the highest pore volume (0.43 cm³/g) was indicated by SBAC, preceded by kaolinite (0.26 cm³/g), which offers increased gas adsorption. The CO₂ adsorption capacity for each of the adsorbent was therefore decreased at higher temperatures. In contrast to the kaolinite samples, sugarcane based activated carbon (SBAC) tends to have greater adsorption sites [17]. We therefore concluded based on these results that the use of activated carbon derived from sugar cane bagasse and kaolinite is a promising CO₂ capture alternative.

REFERENCES

- Sumathi, S., et al., *Optimization of microporous palm shell activated carbon production for flue gas desulphurization: Experimental and statistical studies*. *Bioresource technology*, 2009. **100**(4): p. 1614-1621.
- Arami-Niya, A., et al., *Production of microporous palm shell based activated carbon for methane adsorption: modeling and optimization using response surface methodology*. *Chemical engineering research and design*, 2012. **90**(6): p. 776-784.
- Xie, J., et al., *CO₂ adsorption performance of ZIF-7 and its endurance in flue gas components*. *Frontiers of Environmental Science & Engineering*, 2014. **8**(2): p. 162-168.
- Viswanathan, B., P.I. Neel, and T. Varadarajan, *Methods of activation and specific applications of carbon materials*. India, Chennai, 2009.
- Bachrun, S., et al. *Preparation and characterization of activated carbon from sugarcane bagasse by physical activation with CO₂ gas*. in *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 2016.
- Budi, E., et al., *Adsorption and Pore of Physical-Chemical Activated Coconut Shell Charcoal Carbon*. *MS&E*, 2018. **335**(1): p. 012007.
- Matali, S., et al. *Removal of selected gaseous effluent using activated carbon derived from oil palm waste: An Overview*. in *IEEE Symposium on Business, Engineering, and Industrial Applications*. 2013.
- Ioannidou, O. and A. Zabanitoutou, *Agricultural residues as precursors for activated carbon production—a review*. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 2007. **11**(9): p. 1966-2005.
- Allwar, A. *Characteristics of micro-and mesoporous structure and surface chemistry of activated carbons produced by oil palm shell*. in *International Conference on Chemical, Ecology and Environmental Sciences Proceedings*. 2012.
- Skodras, G., et al., *Enhanced mercury adsorption in activated carbons from biomass materials and waste tires*. *Fuel processing technology*, 2007. **88**(8): p. 749-758.
- Chang, K.-L., et al., *Adsorption studies on the removal of an endocrine-disrupting compound (Bisphenol A) using activated carbon from rice straw agricultural waste*. *Separation Science and Technology*, 2012. **47**(10): p. 1514-1521.
- Lazim, Z.M., et al., *The removal of methylene blue and Remazol Brilliant Blue R dyes by using orange peel and spent tea leaves*. *Jurnal Teknologi*, 2015. **74**(11).
- Ahmad, A. and B. Hameed, *Fixed-bed adsorption of reactive azo dye onto granular activated carbon prepared from waste*. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 2010. **175**(1-3): p. 298-303.
- Nouri, H. and A. Ouederni, *Modeling of the dynamics adsorption of phenol from an aqueous solution on activated carbon produced from olive stones*. *International Journal of Chemical Engineering and Applications*, 2013. **4**(4): p. 254.
- Fat'hi, M.R., et al., *Kinetics and thermodynamic studies for removal of acid blue 129 from aqueous solution by almond shell*. *Journal of Environmental Health Science and Engineering*, 2014. **12**(1): p. 62.
- Teutscherova, N., et al., *Leaching of ammonium and nitrate from Acrisol and Calcisol amended with holm oak biochar: A column study*. *Geoderma*, 2018. **323**: p. 136-145.
- Pellerano, M., et al., *CO₂ capture by adsorption on activated carbons using pressure modulation*. 2009. **1**(1): p. 647-653.

S.O Akpasi is currently a master student of the Department of Chemical Engineering at Durban University of Technology, Steve Biko Campus, Durban, South Africa. He was born on January 17, 1992 in Kano, Nigeria. He obtained his Bachelor of Engineering degree (2014) from the Department of Chemical Engineering in Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. His research focuses on climate change (environmental management).

Aside from being a researcher, he is also a tutor in Durban University of Technology. He has helped many students to develop and understand the concept of chemical engineering fundamentals. He is currently writing a dissertation paper about the “evaluation of kaolinite and activated carbon performance for CO₂ capture”.

Mr. S.O Akpasi has received professional certifications on oil and gas management, project management, and facility management & operations.